

was very high in Turners Asbestos Products Projects and at the National Irrigation Research Station.

The GM collected from Zambia was

identified as *Orseolia oryzivora* by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London. This species was identified from the collections in the Lake Chilwa area of

Malawi in 1974. These findings suggest that GM is distributed throughout the Guinea savannas of Africa. □

Chemical control of grasshoppers in Pakistan

M. A. Zafar, senior subject matter specialist in plant protection, Agricultural Adaptive Research Farm (AARF), Sheikhpura, Pakistan

In some years, grasshopper *Hieroglyphus* spp. cause significant losses to rice nurseries and crops in Pakistan. In 1982 we tested four dusts in doses generally recommended in treatments for grasshopper control at AARF.

Grasshoppers were collected from rice fields and reared at room temperature to achieve a large population of adults of uniform age and size. The dusts were cotton dust (6.3% BHC + 10.4% DDT + 83.3% sulfur), BHC 10%, 1:3 mixture of BHC 10% + DDT 10%, and carbaryl 10%. They were sprinkled on the grasshoppers and rice leaves. In the first trial, 100 grasshoppers were kept in a glass jar without food for 24 h, then were released on fresh food. In the second trial grasshoppers were caged on dusted leaves of

Grasshopper control with different insecticide dusts.^a AARF, Pakistan.

Dust	Dosage	Mortality (%) at indicated hours after treatment				
		1	3	6	12	24
	<i>g/100 grasshoppers</i>	<i>Direct dusting on grasshoppers</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	10	13.7	100	100	100	100
BHC 10%	10	22.3	100	100	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture	10	18.0	100	100	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	10	16.3	100	100	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.6 ^a	0.0 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		7.4	20.9	21.3	28.6	16.8
	<i>kg ai/ha</i>	<i>Feeding on dust-impregnated nursery leaves</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	7.20	3.0	42.7	85.0	100	100
BHC 10%	0.75	8.7	49.7	88.3	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture.	0.31 + 0.94	5.0	41.0	76.3	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	2.00	8.3	46.3	81.7	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.3 ^a	1.6 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		6.0	9.3	13.7	15.4	33.8

^aIn each column, averages followed by common letters are significantly similar at 95% level of confidence. ^bCotton dust is a brand name for the mixture of BHC + DDT + sulfur (3:5:40); the dose of 7.2 kg ai/ha is based on the 48% active ingredient in the formulation.

plants. Insect mortality was recorded 1, 3, 6, 12, and 24 h after treatment. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

With direct dusting, all grasshoppers died in 3 h. With foliar dusting, they died in 12 h. All the dusts were effective (see table). □

Entomophaga grylli destruction of locust *Oxya-hyla intricata* in Vietnam

J. Weiser, V. Matha, N. D. Tryachov, and I. Gelbic, Institute of Entomology, Academy of Science, Prague, Czechoslovakia

The fungus *E. grylli* (Fres.) Batko is the most common Entomophthorales fungus and often is associated with locust and grasshopper outbreaks. Data from Southeast Asia describe an outbreak of *E. grylli* in a *Patanga succinata* population on maize east of Lopburi Province in Thailand. By the end of the rainy season, the fungus had destroyed 90% of the locust population and was found in 9 other acridid pests in Thailand.

1. Germinating conidia of *E. grylli* on the wing of *O. intricata*
Scale = 10 µm.

O. intricata Stål is widely distributed in Southeast Asia — Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, West Malaysia — and some parts of South China. It damages rice and several other crops.

In autumn 1983, dense *O. intricata* populations seriously damaged rice around Hanoi, Vietnam. *E. grylli* infected 85-90% adults and nymphs, which died on the plants. Masses of conidiophores

with conidia appeared on the intersegmental membranes (Fig. 1) and on all thin cuticular areas of the head. Conidia of the papillata type of Lakon, 30-40 × 25-36 µm spread over dead insects and plants. Their length-to-breadth ratio varied. Uniform resting pores 30-40 µm in diam developed inside the infected locusts (Fig. 2).

E. grylli may be an important natural enemy of this locust in local outbreaks. □

2. Resting spores of *E. grylli* from the interior of dead *O. intricata*. Scale = 10 µm.

Effect of planting time on rice panicle bug incidence

R. Saroja and N. Raju, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

Rice panicle bug *Leptocoris acuta* (Thumb) is becoming a major rice pest in Tamil Nadu in the Dec-May and Apr-Aug cropping seasons. Adults and nymphs suck sap from developing grains and cause significant yield loss.

We studied the effect of planting time on panicle bug incidence in a field trial with seven planting dates and four replications in 1983-84 Dec-May season. Twenty-five-day-old, short-duration

TM8089 seedlings were planted in 9-m² plots at 20- × 10cm spacing. Plots were fertilized with 100 kg N/ha (50% basal and 2 equal splits topdressed) and 22-42 kg PK/ha. No crop protection was practiced.

Feeding activity was assessed at harvest by counting the insect's stylet sheaths in the grains obtained from five randomly selected panicles from each plot. Undamaged and damaged grains were counted and damage percentage was calculated. Grain yield also was recorded (see table).

The crop planted on 30 Jan had lowest grain damage and yielded highest. At 20-30% grain damage, yield ranged from 4.3

Effect of planting time on rice panicle bug incidence Tirur, India.

Planting date	Damage grain (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
31 Dec 83	34	3.1
10 Jan 84	29	4.4
20 Jan 84	42	3.7
30 Jan 84	17	5.4
10 Feb 84	23	4.5
20 Feb 84	25	4.3
1 Mar 84	34	3.7

to 4.5 t/ha. When damage exceeded 30%, yield fell to 3.1-3.7 t/ha. Very early and very late crops were prone to panicle bug attack. □

A new record of rice shoot fly in the northwestern hills of India

D. K. Garg, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Almora 263601, India

During a survey of rice nurseries in experimental field plots at Hawalbagh in 1983 kharif (May-Oct), we found plants of various entries yellowed and dried in

patches. Plants had deadhearts and small, whitish maggots were recovered from the base of the stems. The maggots were reared in petri dishes and flies emerged and were identified as rice shoot fly *Atherigona oryzae* Mall. This is the first recorded occurrence of *A. oryzae* in the northwestern hills of India.

Newly hatched shoot fly maggots bore into the stems of young plants and feed inside the central shoot, severing the

apical parts of the plant from the base. The leaf whorl fails to unfold, dries, and falls off.

Preliminary field observations showed that maximum infestation was 3-4 wk after sowing. Rice planted early, in the first week of May, was more severely damaged than normal plantings in the last week of May. There was no infestation in the transplanted crop. □

Mortality of adult brown planthoppers (BPH) in different types of cages used for bioassays of entomopathogenic fungi

R. M. Aguda, senior research assistant, IRRI; M. C. Rombach, research associate, Boyce Thompson Institute (BTI) and Collaborative research fellow, IRRI; B. M. Shepard, entomologist, IRRI; and D. W. Roberts, insect pathologist, BTI

Many hyphomycetous fungal pathogens of the BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål and related leafhopper species have been collected and isolated on artificial media. A suitable bioassay test is necessary to determine the most virulent species and strains of these entomopathogens for use in a biological control program against BPH. In addition, standardized bioassay

techniques that minimize mortality are essential to developing programs for subsequent production and field application of the fungi.

Entomopathogenic fungi invade the insect host through the cuticle, grow in the body cavity, and eventually kill the host. BPH fungal pathogens normally kill the host in 2-7 d. During this time,